

Artistic and Philosophical Factors of Ulugbek Hamdam's Creative Motif

Uralova Dilnoza Murodilla's daughter

FarDu 2nd year basic doctoral student

Article information:

Manuscript received: 28 Oct 2024; **Accepted:** 27 Nov 2024; **Published:** 14 Dec 2024

Abstract: Most of the artist's prose is made up of dream stories. Also, all the characters described in the dream stories are nameless, illuminating their spiritual world rather than their external appearance defines the writer's creative credo. In the writer's dream-stories, the examination of the human inner self is clearly manifested. After all, the main point of reference in the stories of the creator is a person and his heart. The tortures that disturbed the writer's psyche are imprinted in the works through dreams.

Keywords: dream, pathos, story, monologue, landscape, psychological symbol, psyche, external monologue, story.

INTRADUTION

It is known that the world has become virtual since the 1960s. With the science that man has created, he has the ability to create unparalleled discoveries: robots, clones. Humanity's tendency to artificiality began to increase, naturalness began to lose its essence in all aspects, as a result, people's admiration and contemplation of the creatures gifted by nature began to decrease, the decrease of admiration in people caused them to ignore the essence of their dreams. With the development of intelligence in all aspects, man began to move to the principle of self-isolation. Considering that man is a complex creature, a phenomenon that no one has yet been able to fully study, the same is true of his inner self: his feelings and thoughts have no limits, therefore, dreams that pass in the unconscious state. The essence of the dream has not yet been fully understood. The fact that the dream motif does not choose a place and time allows to express the artistic idea that the creators want to express in a wide scope.

LITERATURE ANALYSIS AND METHODOLOGY

As Sigmund Freud pointed out, "Dreams are the realization of our unthinkable desires that are waiting in front of us". Man was given a perfect form by the creator, and they all move through the medium of the spirit. When the soul leaves a person, the movement of all organs stops, so the artist pays great attention to the issue of the soul. The human spirit is still a phenomenon that has not been fully studied. Also, self-cultivation is important in the moral maturity of a person. Self-cultivation has always been of primary importance in Eastern philosophy, and in the work of our great scholars and mystics, it was considered as the main criterion of human spiritual perfection. In the teachings of Islam, great importance is attached to the purity of the soul in the perfection of the individual. In the Holy Qur'an, Surah Fajr, verse 27: "O peaceful soul! Return to your Lord as you are pleased with Him! and in the 16th verse of Surah Taghobun, it is blessed: "...whoever can avoid the greed of his own self, those are the ones who will be saved".

A significant part of the scholars and thinkers of the East left valuable wisdom about self-discipline. In particular, a large part of Jalaluddin Rumi's work is occupied by wisdom related to the purity of the soul. Maulana about the self: "If you refrain from fulfilling the desires of the self, you will reach your eternal desire and get rid of this darkness, prison". In the explanatory dictionary of the Uzbek language, nafs is explained as follows: "Nafs (Arabic nafs-qalb, heart; human being; goal; pride, pride). "The writer's story "A cup of water" is written in accordance with the wisdom of great mystics. At the heart of the story, what is the purpose of a person coming to this bright world? The essence of the story is to understand what tasks and assignments are assigned to him.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

We all know that the author considered Jalaluddin Rumi as his spiritual teacher and enriched the treasury of our literature with a rare work by skilfully translating the work of Maulana "Ichindagi Ichindadur". At the same time, at the heart of every story of the writer, the Romanian view, the breath of Romanian philosophy can be felt. The work was created as a direct dedication to the Sultan of Meanings, Jalaluddin Rumi. The story "The man who opened and closed his eyes" also belongs to the series of dream stories of the writer. Through the proverbs in the story, a person realizes the meaning of the creation along with the realization of his identity. The story is written in the style of an internal monologue. Hearing that his teacher has gone to the eternal world, the hero sets off on a journey without a horse to follow him to his final destination. Reality takes the leading position in the plot lines through the dream motif. At the beginning of the journey, our hero, who encountered a strange crossroads, is surprised that no matter where he goes in the world, all roads lead to the land of his teacher. Surprised that all roads lead to the teacher, the hero reaches the land where different nationalities of the world are gathered. When he came out in front of the coffin with a blue cloth thrown in it, he looked as if he had found his teacher, his face turned black, he regretted that he was a great man of the country he went to, and he left for another country. In other parts of the world, the hero who searches for his mentor after meeting representatives of different faces, colors, and religions, gets tired both physically and mentally. Tired of the many roads, the hero begins to look for one way, his own way. The hero, who is tired of trying all the ways of the world, suddenly, standing in the middle of the square, his blue eyes involuntarily turn towards the blue, and the example of a bird with its hands ready to fly begins to rotate with its whole body, pointing one to the sky and the other to the ground.

CONCLUSION

With the development of intelligence in all aspects, man began to move to the principle of self-isolation. Considering that man is a complex creature, a phenomenon that no one has yet been able to fully study, the same is true of his inner self: his feelings and thoughts have no limits, therefore, dreams that pass in the unconscious state. The essence of the dream has not yet been fully understood. The fact that the dream motif does not choose a place and time allows to express the artistic idea that the creators want to express in a wide scope.

List of references

1. Dzhorakulov U. Abstract feelings // World literature. -Tashkent, 2003. Oct. - B.159.
2. Yoldoshev K. Painful feeling and restless spirit. // Hot word. Tashkent: new century generation, 2006, - B. 511.
3. Karim B. Ulugbek's heart expression. // Distant Dilnura. T.: Akademnashr, 2010. - B. 3.
4. Yoldoshev K. Painful feeling and restless spirit. // Hot word. Tashkent: new century generation, 2006, - B. 511.
5. Karim B. Ulugbek's heart expression. // Distant Dilnura. T.: Akademnashr, 2010. - B. 3.
6. Sabirdinov A. Sources of spirituality and enlightenment - Tashkent. Academic edition.: 2016.
7. Eshankulov J. Dream and its artistic wave in Uzbek folklore.f.f.d. diss. abstract, -T., 2010.